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Management of postoperative pain in upper abdominal bariatric laparoscopic surgery. External oblique intercostal (EOI) block for rescue analgesia

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Letter to the Editor

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Fascial plane blocks are becoming an important part of multimodal analgesia with their widespread use and beneficial postoperative effects. Many fascial plane blocks have been described in the last decade. They are also methods used by physicians who struggle with postoperative pain, especially in rescue analgesia. External intercostal (EOI) block was first described in 2021 by Elsharkawy et al. [1].

We aim to present the EOI block which we apply as a successful rescue analgesia after bariatric surgery.

The patient was a 27-year-old morbidly obese female who weighed 140 kg, was 170 cm tall, and had a BMI of 48.4. The patient was scheduled for laparoscopic gastric sleeve surgery for weight loss. After the induction of general anesthesia, the operation was started with mechanical ventilator support and halogenated volatile agent maintenance. A total of 400 mcg fentanyl was administered intraoperatively. Paracetamol 1 g and tramadol 100 mg intravenously were administered 30 minutes before the end of the operation. The patient was agitated in the postoperative care unit and expressed that her pain was unbearable. She expressed her pain as 10 on the numeric rating scale (NRS). We decided to apply a bilateral EOI block to reduce the patient's upper abdominal pain.

Written consent for the procedure and publication has been obtained from the patient.

A linear ultrasound transducer (12–15 MHz, Esaote MyLab Five) was placed in the sagittal plane between the midclavicular and anterior axillary lines at the level of the 6th rib, 2 cm medial to the anterior axillary line, then slightly rotated clockwise as a paramedian sagittal oblique, and the 6th and 7th ribs were visualized in a short axis. The

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patient, being more comfortable both in intraoperative and postoperative periods.

Considering that the somatic pain component is more dominant in laparoscopic surgery, EOI block includes the advantage of blocking both the lateral and anterior branches of the nerves supplying the upper abdominal somatic areas.

It also allows for the reduction of opioid consumption and its harmful effects, which is very important in morbidly obese patients.

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Ethics

Informed Consent

Written informed consent was obtained from both patients for publication of this case report, including the use of anonymized clinical data and images.

Author Contributions

The author is solely responsible for the conception, design, data acquisition, analysis, interpretation, and drafting of the manuscript.

Declaration of Interests

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

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